

A Teaching Model for Undergraduates Based on Program Outcomes: A Survey on the Teaching and Learning Process at Ba Ria – Vung Tau University

Quoc Van Le, Ph.D.

Faculty of Tourism and Health, Ba Ria – Vung Tau University, Viet Nam

ABSTRACT: The paper proposes how to build a teaching model that combines subject's outcome standards, lesson plans, assessment and technology-based approach to better support students' self-regulated learning (SSRL). The formative assessment method is combined with the summative assessment method in the teaching process with the goal of meeting the maximum output standards of the course objectives built for the course. The lesson plan is designed to be flexible in combination with technology to help students' self-regulated learning and achieve the subject objectives in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes. The paper surveys second-year students at Ba Ria - Vung Tau University. Results from observations and surveys show that lecturers have not been able to link the above these factors to help students achieve all three outcome standards of knowledge, skills and attitudes.

KEYWORDS: *outcome standards, teaching model, students' self-regulated learning (SSRL)*

INTRODUCTION

Frequently, when people talk about the innovation in teaching methods, they often think of the innovation in contents, curriculum, teaching and learning methods, especially modern teaching aids such as technology and/or equipment. All of them help teachers teach better, but not necessarily towards the benefit of learners if they are still learning passively like studying in high school programs. However, the goal of university teaching is to help learners discover their own knowledge, skills and attitudes towards their own learning goals. According to personal observations, the teaching of the University currently has three main disadvantages: (1) the traditional teaching method, which is lecture (teacher's presentation), is still widely used; (2) has not focused on training positive attitude in SSRL for students. (3) the form of assessment through midterm and final exams has not brought into play the creativity and independent thinking for students.

Although the implementation of the training program follows the outcome standards, the subjects have identified the training program objectives in which, emphasize on equipping students with professional knowledge, skills and attitudes, in the process of implementation in each subject, the outcome standards of each subject do not follow the training program, especially the attitude is often ignored because, during the teaching process, the teacher has not designed the lesson and has an assessment method to ensure the outcome standard of the subject.

Technology has always played an important role in teaching. Recently, after the Covid 19 pandemic, online learning has become a major and important activity in most universities in Vietnam. Many instructors have preferred to teach online and have found that the online classroom can be taught as well or better than the traditional classroom. Learning support systems can be used to store lectures, interact, discuss between teachers and students or students and students very effectively. Students have many opportunities to familiarize themselves with technology tools, search for knowledge, analyze and create content, handle situations more effectively, and have a sense of self-study, teamwork, and projects.

In fact, in the digital age, although knowledge, skills and attitudes are three different but closely related components. Knowledge is the facts, ideas, evidence, and descriptions of processes or procedures contained in the curriculum, while skills are requirements in the society such as the input analysis, self-study, teamwork, critical thinking, problem solving, creativity, digital skills, management. Attitude includes willing, honesty and responsibility of the students.

Developing an effective learning environment for students in a module is one of the most important parts of teaching, so the course must focus on learners, learning objectives, learning activities, learning support requirements, test strategies for assessment, and learning control. Therefore, the role of the teacher is to build and take full advantage of this environment in the teaching process, especially in the process of designing lessons to improve teaching and learning efficiency. The article provides an objective and

practical view to gradually build and perfect a learning management system and to help students learn reasons and learning methods more effectively and conveniently to meet their needs' outcome standards of the training program and their own output standards.

METHODS

The article uses the method of classroom observation, investigation of the training process, and a questionnaire to describe the current situation and compare it with the proposed model. The data collected through the questionnaire were analyzed by using descriptive statistics in which a Likert Scale was used to measure the students' responses. The response options are scaled as follow: '5' for strongly agree, '4' for agree, '3' for neutral, '2' for disagree and '1' for strongly disagree. From there, analyze the existing resources and propose solutions to develop and apply the training model to meet the outcome standards for stakeholders.

Fig.1. Theoretical analysis

Hypothesis

- If there is a relationship between TG and OS in teaching and learning process.
- If there is a relationship between LP and OS in teaching and learning process.
- If there is a relationship between TB and OS in teaching and learning process.
- If there is a relationship between AS and OS in teaching and learning process.

RESULTS

Firstly, looking at teachers' factors, the results in table 1 shows that 100% teachers' perceptions are in neutral agreement (M = 2.86). However, technology-based approach, lesson plans, teaching goals are used for teaching in the neutral agreement while assessment is in the disagreement (M = 2.42). It means that the teacher is not satisfied with their teaching assessment.

Table 1 Teacher's factors towards the teaching model

No.	Teacher's factors	N=4	
		M	SD
1	Teaching goals	2.76	.77
2	Lesson plans	2.87	.62
3	Technology-based	3.39	.82
4	Assessment	2.42	.74
	Total	2.86	.74

Note: M: mean; SD: Standard deviation

Secondly, the results in table 2 express a picture of neutral agreement (M = 2.92) that the students think they can achieve their outcome standards. However, the mean of the students' attitudes is the lowest value.

Table 2. Students’ factors towards outcome standards

No.	Students’ Factors	N=60	
		M	SD
1	Knowledge	3.20	.72
2	Skills	2.81	.69
3	Attitudes	2.76	.67
	Total	2.92	.69

Note: M: mean; SD: Standard deviation

The author hopes to know clearly which exact factors of the students’ knowledge, skills and attitudes are satisfied. In table 3, the students’ knowledge is just in remembering, understanding and applying competence (level 3 in Bloom’s taxonomy).

Table 3. Students’ knowledge towards outcome standards

No.	Students’ knowledge	N=60	
		M	SD
1	Remember	3.45	.68
2	Understand	3.55	.75
3	Apply	3.22	.78
4	Analyze	2.33	.72
5	Evaluate	2.23	.70
6	Creative	2.12	.69
	Total	3.20	.72

Note: M: mean; SD: Standard deviation

In table 4, the students are not satisfied with problem solving, group work, and presentation skills because their mean scores are in disagreeing levels.

Table 4. Students’ skills towards outcome standards

No.	Students’ skills	N=60	
		M	SD
1	Listening	3.45	.68
2	Communication	3.55	.75
3	Time management	3.22	.68
4	Problem solving	2.33	.63
5	Group work	2.23	.71
6	Presentation	2.12	.69
	Total	2.81	.69

Note: M: mean; SD: Standard deviation

In table 5, it is evident that students’ attitudes are measured highly in neutral agreement with truth, willing to learn, acknowledgement and hopefulness values. However, the value of the students’ cooperation and discipline are not good enough.

Table 5. Students’ attitudes towards outcome standards

No.	Students’ attitudes	N=60	
		M	SD
1	Truth	3.35	.62
2	Willing to learn	3.01	.64
3	Acknowledgement	2.89	.73
4	Hopefulness	2.86	.67
5	Cooperation	2.25	.71
6	Discipline	2.23	.67
	Total	2.76	.67

Note: M: mean; SD: Standard deviation

In table 6, The P-value for the correlation results of all the variables against the decision to achieve OS was .000. The P-value scores confirmed that all the variables examined have an impact on achieving OS. The P-value of .000 proved that all variables are significantly correlated.

Table 6. Summary of accepted and rejected hypotheses.

Hypotheses	P	Decision
If there is a relationship between TG and OS in teaching and learning process.	.000	Accept
If there is a relationship between LP and OS in teaching and learning process.	.000	Accept
If there is a relationship between TB and OS in teaching and learning process.	.000	Accept
If there is a relationship between AS and OS in teaching and learning process.	.000	Accept

DISCUSSIONS

From the results of the questionnaire, the author compares with the classroom observations and documental training process. The author saw that there are some strong and weak points of the teachers’ teaching goals and the students’ outcome standards. Although the teachers have textbooks, materials, teaching aims, lesson plans and adapting technology in teaching, their assessment is not good enough. One of the main reasons is that their tests are not matched rigorously with the outcome standards, and the tests often focus on checking understanding, remembering and applying. However, in Bloom’s taxonomy, it suggests that undergraduates’ outcome standards must be in analyzing levels or higher levels.

In addition, the students’ skills in problem solving and work in group and presentation as well as their attitudes of cooperation and discipline are not good. According to the author’s observation during learning and teaching in classroom, the teachers rarely suggest them work in group or separate them into small groups to discuss or cooperate problems, they even do not have any chance to study themselves by the task-based or project-based. These reasons can be causes that make the students’ attitudes toward SSRL worse and worse. The teachers don’t control the SSRL or guide them how to learn in groups, so their motivation in learning is not high enough to meet the outcome standards.

CONCLUSION

From the teaching model, three out of four factors of the teachers are accepted or satisfied, they are teaching goals, lesson plans and technology. It means that the factor of the teachers’ assessment should be improved to make the student get higher learning motivation and SSRL.

With the students' factors, looking at the outcome standards, they just reach the level three of knowledge, skills of listening, communication, time management, and attitudes of truth, willing to learn, acknowledgement, hopefulness.

From the results, the paper suggests that if the teachers can improve their assessment and control the SSRL by showing them projects or tasks to help them learn in groups and cooperate effectively.

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Cite this Article: Quoc Van Le (2023). A Teaching Model for Undergraduates Based on Program Outcomes: A Survey on the Teaching and Learning Process at Ba Ria – Vung Tau University. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 6(5), 2757-2761